

Synchronous Self-healing and Self-sensing in an Opto-Vascular Structural Thermoset

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Outline

- **Background / Motivation**
- **Foundational Opto-Vascular Elements**
- ***In situ* self-healing**
- **Autonomous damage detection and repair**
- **Summary**

Motivation: Damage and Bioinspired Self-healing, Self-sensing

Multi-scale fracture

Fiber-reinforced composite

Compos. Sci. Technol. **64** (2004)

Micro-cracking

Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A **374** (2016)

Interlaminar delamination

Polymer **53** (2012)

Self-healing – repair internal damage

Nature **540** (2016)

Microcapsules

- ✓ autonomic
- ✗ single heal

Nature **409** (2001)

Two-part agent limitations:

Diffusion-dominated reaction is **slow** (*i.e.*, days)

Adv. Mater **26** (2014)

Propensity for **cross-contamination** of two-part agents (*i.e.*, blockages) limits number of repeat heal cycles

Adv. Mater. **22** (2010)

Microvascular

- ✓ multiple cycles
- ✓ large damage

Nat. Mater. **6** (2007)

Science **344** (2014)

Self-sensing – report damage / recovery

Electrical

Nature Nanotechnol. **7** (2012)

Optical

Sci. Adv. **8** (2022)

Research Approach: "Opto-vascular" Self-healing & Self-sensing

- **Question:** Can *repeatable* self-healing and self-sensing be achieved in a structural polymer?

Photopolymerization

- Monomer
- Initiator

Free-radical

- ✓ Rapid cure (minutes)
- ✗ Oxygen inhibition
- ✗ Weak bonding to epoxy
- ✗ High shrinkage

Cationic

- ~ Slower cure (minutes-hour)
- ✓ Oxygen insensitive
- ✓ Superior bonding to epoxy
- ✓ Low shrinkage

Development of a Visible-light Photo-active Healing Agent

- Epoxy-based cationic photochemistry formulated to polymerize with visible (405 nm) light.

Cationic formulation

Monomers:

1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether

bisphenol A diglycidyl ether

Photo-Initiator:

diphenyliodonium salt

Toughener:

star-block copolymer

Sensitizer:

9,10-diehoxyanthracene

UV-Vis spectroscopy

Parallel-plate rheometry

Raman spectroscopy

Photochemical conversion

Mechanical Evaluation: Mode-I Fracture

- Tapered Double Cantilever Beam (TDCB) to assess self-healing efficiency (η).

Vascular TDCB

Autonomous fluid delivery

ex situ healing

Fracture behavior

Healing Efficiency[†] (η)

$$\eta = \frac{K_{IC}^{healed}}{K_{IC}^{virgin}} = \frac{P_c^{healed}}{P_c^{virgin}}$$

[†] *Exp. Mech.* **42** (2002)

ex situ healing baseline

[‡] *Adv. Mater.* **26** (2014)

In situ Self-healing Experiments

- Fiber-coupled laser diode (405 nm) and optical components for *in situ* mechanical recovery.

TDCB sample in load frame

Light intensity vs. exposure time tradeoff

(optimizing photo-acid diffusion with constant dose)

Fluorescent microscopy – full dose

Adhesive failure (high degree of cure)

Cohesive failure (low degree of cure)

Leveraging *In situ* Dark Cure

- Diffusion of unconsumed photo-acid allows for continued polymerization after removing light source

Integrated Damage Sensing and Optical Recovery

- Orthogonal sensing modality to interrogate system state w/o inducing polymerization.

Autonomous and Repeatable Sensing + Healing

- Automated and consistent healing/sensing over multiple cycles via microcontroller integration.

Optical sensing feedback control for autonomy

Healing agent accumulation on fracture surface

Autonomous and repeatable self-healing

Effect of Light Dose on Repeated Healing

- Ensuring consistent dose to maintain healing efficiency over multiple cycles

One heal cycle ($250 \text{ mW cm}^{-2} \times 90 \text{ min} = 1.35 \text{ kJ cm}^{-2}$)

Three heal cycles - Constant time (90 min)

Three heal cycles - Constant dose (1.35 kJ cm⁻²)

Self-healing summary

Summary

- **New** “Opto-vascular” platform **overcomes limitations** of two-part microvascular healing.
- **In situ** photo-polymerization achieves **> 90% recovery** of fracture toughness (K_{IC}) in a structural epoxy.
- **Rapid** self-healing (90 min.) is **~30x faster** than prior two-part systems (48 h).
- **Orthogonal** sensing modality (660 nm) provides **damage + healing** monitoring.
- **Autonomous** repair functionality enabled via **microcontroller** integration.
- **Sustained healing** over multiple cycles **possible** with **light dosing control** via fiber sensor

Phillips et al. Opto-vascular Synchrony for Autonomous Self-healing and Self-sensing in a Structural Thermoset. *In Prep.* (2025)

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Questions?

International Conference of Self-healing Materials (ICSHM2026)

ICSHM

10th International Conference on Self-healing Materials
July 8-10
Drexel University, Philadelphia, USA

Event highlights:

- Connect with experts and peers from around the world
- Discover emerging technologies, methods, and applications
- Present your latest research and gain valuable feedback
- Explore historic city - Philadelphia, PA birthplace of the United States

 July 8-10, 2026

 Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA, USA

 <https://icshm2026.org>

Abstract Submission Open: Now
Abstract Submission Close: 15 February 2026

JULY 8-10

ICSHM

10th International Conference on Self-healing Materials

Conference Chairs

Prof. Jason Patrick
(NC State University)

Prof. Amir Farnham
(Drexel University)

Investigating Host Opacity

- Progress towards self-healing in opaque composites (e.g., carbon fiber).

Translucent (neat epoxy)

Opaque (epoxy + carbon black)

Active exposure + dark cure

Questions?

Leveraging *In situ* Dark Cure

- Diffusion of unconsumed photo-acid allows for continued polymerization after removing light source

Raman spectroscopy – continued conversion

$$D = D^*$$

Active exposure + dark cure

$$D \leq D^*$$

Reduced active exposure + dark cure

$$t_{\Delta} = 90 - t_a^*$$

Questions?

Active exposure only

Active + dark cure - full exposure

Active + dark cure - partial exposure

Backup
